

Estrangement in Fadia Faqir's My Name is Salma

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Abstract

This study investigates estrangement as the individual's feeling of separation and loneliness from oneself, others and, the native place where estrangement takes many forms, such as social, physical, and cultural estrangement. Estrangement is a characteristic that distinguishes a person and is described as a natural phenomenon and sometimes is labeled as a pathological phenomenon. It is also described as a multidimensional phenomenon due to its philosophical, social, psychological, and even literary uses. The increasing number of estrangement cases, commonly in developing countries such as Jordan, requires serious academic analysis not only because the victims' lives are at stake, but also because the phenomenon of estrangement is still gravely unaddressed and overlooked due to religious and socio-cultural norms labeling it as a social and cultural taboo. Of late, there has been growing interest among Middle Eastern, Arab, and Jordanian researchers and writers in portraying estrangement through their literary works (Maher, 2018). Thus, in this paper, we shall examine the manifestations of estrangement in the Jordanian context through a textual analysis of My Name is Salma by Fadia Faqir, an author considered one of the founding figures of the contemporary literary movement in Jordan. Originally written in English, this novel highlights the suffering of a Jordanian woman due to the fear of being a victim of the honor killing at the hands of her tribal family in a male-controlled society. Through social, patriarchal, and Islamic readings to analyze My Name is Salma (2007), we shall examine Faqir's depictions of the phenomenon of estrangement in the novel as an extremely engendered phenomenon resultant from male domination and gender inequity prevalent in the Jordanian society. This paper is premised based on the analysis of the estrangement and its association with a Muslim woman, as depicted in My Name is Salma through the novel's female character, particularly the main protagonist, Salma.

Introduction

Estrangement as a cultural and social issue, if carefully taken into consideration, is on the rise in recent years due to its aspects affecting the person in various areas of life, especially as it is related to the rapid development witnessed by the human society between East and West. Estrangement "is a widespread social problem and phenomena in Middle Eastern, Arab and Islamic societies such as Jordan where male domination and gender inequality are the main pillars of these societies, alongside a disparity of Islamic teachings' application in the lifestyles of the men and women" (Ali, 2018, p.1). With the growing number of Jordanian figures and writers who experience the suffering related to the concept of estrangement, several literary movements in the Arab world such as the Arab Writers Association and the Jordanian Writers Association have ranked Jordan as the best example in terms of the prevalence of phenomena of estrangement (Susan, 2016). Thus, the issue of estrangement is not a product of Faqir's imagination, but rather a truth depicted in the *My Name is Salma* on the realities of contemporary Jordan.

Over the past decades, Jordanian women have been victims of the oppression practiced by a patriarchal society. A male whether he is a father, a husband, a son, and a brother believes that he is the one who has the power over a female whether she is a mother, a wife, and a daughter, and a sister. This mentality is an offshoot of the belief that women are only required for birth and reproduction (Khan, 2015). Therefore, Jordanian women suffer complex oppression, especially after the outbreak of the new tribal tradition and norms which are standing apart from Islamic teachings. Accordingly, several women resort to escape as an expected result of such social and complex construction as it is the only passage to embark on a new life away from all forms of violence, oppression, and gender inequality. In a patriarchal society, the reputation of the family or tribe lies only in women's moral and social behaviors. Of note, males' mistakes and vices are ignored and forgotten, and even glorified as depicted by the famous Jordanian proverb, "Man is a strength and woman is a weakness" (Qadi,

2017, p.7). As such, it is not a surprise that several characters have opted to migrate and escape from this unending cycle of patriarchal domination. Yet, they, unfortunately, begin suffering from physical, social, and cultural estrangement.

“To accomplish a platform of empowerment to raise awareness among the Jordanian women concerning their rights and bridge the gap of gender inequalities between men and women, several literary figures especially those of the Jordanian contemporary movement such as Fadia Faqir have used fiction to highlight the despair of Jordanian women” (Al Ghammaz, Ruzy Suliza Hashim, Amrah Abdulmajid, 2020, p.3). In a message to male perpetrators and violence committers in Jordan, Faqir, through *My Name is Salma*, has explicitly succeeded to depict the misery and dilemma of estrangement resulting from the repeated acts of violence and fears of being a victim of honor killing. Set in Hima in the north of Jordan, Beirut, Lebanon, and Exeter in Britain, *My Name is Salma* revolves around Salma, the main character in the novel that resists the image of the Bedouin girl lurking inside her after many years of her escape from her Jordanian village, Hima to the British city of Exeter because of a relationship with a young relative whose name is Hamdan. As a result of this out of marriage relationship, Salma gives birth to a girl whose name is Leila whom Salma will never see after her birth because Salma is in prison, aiming to protect her from the oppression of her family whose reputation is tarnished because of her scandalous act. While living in Exeter, Salma cannot get rid of the memories of pain, violence, torture, cruelty, and the feelings of estrangement in her first community, although she starts a family after years of homelessness in Britain through marrying a British man named John. After Salma gives birth to a baby, she immediately decides to return to Hima to search for her daughter, whom she has never seen before, discovering that her daughter has been previously killed by her uncle because of her mother’s act of giving birth to her. Later on, Salma is also killed by her brother for the same reason. Through her heroine, Faqir offers a harsh critique of estrangement as a catastrophic practice suffered by several women due to the unjustified social patriarchal practices prevailing in Jordan.

1. Contextualizing Estrangement:

Considering the Arab community society of oppression and domination in an absolute and natural way, especially concerning women and the view of society to them and their presence in it, many Arab women resort to emigration to the West and here Arab female immigrants are exposed to estrangement in all its forms, misery, injustice and prejudice in the diaspora. Estrangement, however, is motivated by emotional, psychological, and social factors. As Haddad (2014, p. 6) argues, “the victimized migrants suffering from estrangement are only limited to women because their families featured with the tribal mentality do not feel accept any heinous or scandalous behaviors such emotional or sexual relationship with a strange male because such an action is considered as a stab to the family’s entity.”

In patriarchal societies such as the Arab societies in general and the Jordanian society in particular, males are given a round of applause for practicing their freedom whereas females are deprived of their least independent rights. “Females are under intense scrutiny since young, and any misstep is considered dishonorable to the family and society is punishable by death. A patriarchal social construction encourages a man to control his family through force as a means of discipline” (Al Ghammaz, Ruzy Suliza Hashim, Amrah Abdulmajid, 2020, p.6). Contemporary female migrants live an unfamiliar shock of estrangement under the influence of the massive booms of change and transformation in various aspects of life and the components of social and cultural existence, along with living in a new remote place away from the birthplace such as moving to live from east to west. Worth mentioning, these massive transformations in contemporary human society have been described under exciting headings such as post-globalization estrangement or Post-migration estrangement.

In the face of this tremendous tide of waves of estrangement and isolation, the original and social culture and even religious beliefs are no longer able to withstand Western rationalism sweeping and swallowing everything around it, especially women without eliminating them, i.e. rationality that storms the borders without permission and causes an imbalance in the psychological, social, cultural and religious balance. All-female Arab Muslim immigrants inside the bottleneck neither are they able to close their windows and deafen their ears to what is happening in the world nor are they able to rely on their historical and religious composition and intellectual equation to continue and resist. Therefore, it is these women who bear the brunt of this tragic situation far from their homeland. With that, estrangement is prevalent among Muslim and Arab women from various countries such as Egypt, Iraq, Lebanon, Syria, Palestine, and especially Jordan.

As Omar (2016) contends that the concept of endings is minted as a new formula for expressing shock and wonder to these women due to the existing social, religious and cultural differences between the easterners and westerners, leading the intellectuals and writers to conduct more studies and literature to send strong and warning letters to these immigrant women and their societies about the horrible ends resulting from this estrangement.

Yasin (2013) argues that amid this rapture and the round of human change, with its revolutions, transformations, endings, and aspects of its strength, the cultural and religious questions raise itself strongly: Where is the human religious culture and what is its role amid an era full of religious and cultural gaps? What role does this culture play in preserving the image of a lost female migrant between two opposing personalities? Where is the position

of these women in this contemporary capitalist Western culture? And to what extent will these women who are culturally, socially, and religiously lost live in a cycle of cultural isolation and estrangement?

Truthfully, the consequences of estrangement are culturally, physically, and socially harmful due to the family collusion in these conditions that are planned acts of killings. Migrant women fleeing unjust masculine societies are in reality facing the shock of the cultural estrangement trying to destroy their noble human and religious values. With the continuation of this devastating extension of the culture of estrangement, these contemporary Arab Muslim women find themselves in a cycle of unique cultural and religious subjugation characterized by the nature of complexity, distance, and duplication. And if Western women live in a single expatriate culture, represented by the culture of modernity and globalization and its aftermath, Arab Muslim women will live in the shadow of two expatriate cultures, where they find themselves between the struggle of modernity and the traditional social culture and its ability to kill and weaken those women as they were stuck between a rock and a hard place.

The prevailing traditional Arab culture, stressing the prevalent culture in its anthropological sense, has turned into a unique model of backwardness culture in all its cultural and social backwardness meanings such as its ability to deprive helpless women of their awareness, freedom, and independence. It is not an irony to the truth to say in this regard that this culture imposes on these women many wrong values such as the violence, submission, surrender, and the dark past featured with intolerance, domination, and fear. In other words, traditional culture instills the values of submission to the fait accompli, reinforces the deep presence of patriarchy, and the absence of critical spirit. Based on this ugly picture of the commonness of estrangement among the Arab and Jordanian women in the West, it is well-timed to see how it is represented in the contemporary Jordanian literature.

2. Literature Review:

Fadia Faqir is a Jordanian author who was born and educated in Amman, Jordan. She gained a BA in English Literature from the University of Jordan before her departure to Britain in 1984 to complete her MA in Creative Writing at Lancaster University. In 1990, the University of East Anglia awarded her the first doctorate in creative and critical writing. Faqir is a contemporary creative writer who has produced seven novels, six short stories, nine chapters in academic books, essays, and memoirs. In her works, Faqir is interested in women's studies in the Middle East through the Center for Middle Eastern and Islamic Studies at Durham University. Since then, she has been interested in fictional writing and teaching creative writing and is currently a fellow writer at St Aiden College, Durham University. Faqir's works are the subject of academic research and discussions related to the life of women in the third world and Arab countries, Arab migrant women, estrangement, and other issues of human rights. Faqir's novels provide candid reflections on the reality of the social crises and other problems related to the status of women in Jordan. The way the writer addresses the subject matter of estrangement with all its forms reflects the unceasing cycle of estrangement and the extent to which Jordanian women face the consequences of estrangement in their communities and overseas. Estrangement as a social and cultural ill is not an offshoot of Faqir's imaginative talents in prose writing, but rather a reality unaffectedly depicted in *My Name is Salma*.

In her 2016 study, *Powerless Women in Faqir's My Name is Salma*, Susan confirms the fact that like several Arab and Eastern countries, Jordan's social construction is structured as a tribal and patriarchal society powered by the families, along with their rigid beliefs concerning the treatment of women. She also assumes that Faqir's depiction of the heroine, Salma reveals the marginalized image of Jordanian women who are viewed by their partners and the society as a naive individual who only concerns about eating, drinking, ultimate obedience to men, and giving birth. Susan also highlights how the society aspires to see women making mistakes, problems, and vices to condemn them and reaffirm the already firm social belief that the spark of corruption in society begins with the corruption of women. According to Susan, the male-controlled atmosphere in the Jordanian culture is often powered by the misinterpretation and malpractice of the teachings of Islam which list males over females in all aspects of life.

As for the academic scholarship of estrangement in fiction, few noteworthy studies have been selected for this study's literature review. In her 2016 study, *Estrangement's Depiction in Khalifeh's 1997 novel The Inheritance*, Malik asserts that the novel is a clear representation of the phenomenon of estrangement among Jordanian women. He reaffirms that Khalifeh is not hesitant to show her anger about the bad experience of estrangement suffered by Arab female migrants in general and Jordanian female migrants in particular which can be anything but horrible. Malik also maintains that this social ill shall be healthily and systematically addressed by the families of these Jordanian female migrants falling apart due to the phenomenon of estrangement.

In his 2015 study, *Estrangement's Elements in Hanan Al-Shaykh's 1980 novel The Story of Zahra*, Ronny presents a more detailed perception of the phenomenon in Jordan, reaffirming how estrangement is socially embedded due to the outdated social beliefs and traditions that empower males over females in all aspects of life. Regardless of the different pretexts and contexts are given by victims to estrangement in the aforesaid literary works, Faqir's *My Name is Salma* shares a sense of universal accord that estrangement is socially driven

and empowered, and Islam is the only solution to those migrants falling victims to estrangement. Against this and due to the nature of the estrangement as an activity practiced in an Islamic context, the Islamic viewpoint represented in the Holy Qur'an is factored as a conceptual framework in this paper to make evident that the roots and motives of the act of estrangement are socially embedded and Islam is the religion that presents valid and practical solutions to social and personal problems to Muslims anywhere and anytime.

3. Conceptual Framework:

Islam is a religion fit for every-time and place through the old and new history. The Islamic Religion's Holy Qur'an is a heavenly constitution and a divine law that presents guidance to all issues of human and social life. The Islamic religion provides realistic solutions to social, personal, economic, and political problems. Islam is featured with its adaptability to meet new emergent problems and complexities related to the male and female Muslims' daily personal and social experiences.

Islam is a religion of justice and mercy for all people, and the evidence is gleaned from the Holy Qur'an as Allah says "And we have not sent you, [O Muhammad], except as a mercy to the worlds" (21:107). Not only Islam is limited to organizing the relationship between a Muslim and a non-Muslim from the people of the same state, but also defines the social and personal principles and foundations upon which the relationship between a Muslim and a non-Muslim among peoples outside the state because Islam is a universal religion for every time and place (Rushdi Anwar, 2011).

Several social and cultural problems experienced by Muslims are resultant from other cultural and social restrictions and complexities considered new experiences to Muslims living in western countries. The fundamental differences in the way of thinking and behavior between East and West have caused many psychological and personal disturbances, imbalances and estrangement among Muslims residing in the West, leading to the abandonment of many Islamic values that govern and fine-tune their relations with other non-Muslims.

From an Islamic perspective, estrangement like many social phenomena leads to the collapse of the values of Muslims on several occasions and various places. However, this collapse in preserving values shall not last more as Muslims are required to preserve and sustain their teachings of Islam. From an Islamic insight, estrangement reflects the structural ethical and social imperfections in Arab and Islamic societies, where tribal and familial customs shall not prevail in a society dominated by Islam. From an Islamic viewpoint, the rising number of cases of estrangement among Arab Muslims in western countries is viewed as a wake-up call to Muslims required to be good examples in behaviors to others in the west, and not fall apart due to the gap between the eastern and western culture prevailing in the western countries. Islam, which Muslims take pride in belonging to, is a civilized religion, which rejects all forms of ugliness and chaos and always pushes the Muslim to live in a clean society to accept others, initiate work and production and encourage him/her to live a good life with his /her family and all those around him/her, especially migrant Muslims living in the western countries.

More importantly, the Holy Qur'an, which is the approved source of Islam, encompasses several verses clarifying the Islamic standpoint relating to the social ill of estrangement. The Holy Qur'an says "O mankind, indeed we have created you from male and female and made you peoples and tribes that you may know one another (49:13). In another example from the Qur'anic verses is when Allah says "And if your Lord had willed, He could have made mankind one community; but they will not cease to differ" (11:118).

In detail, the said Qur'anic verse asserts that acceptance of the other in the western countries is required to exchange of benefits and ideas, but without abandoning the religious values of the Muslim required to be a good, strong and polite example for others, especially the persecuted Arab Muslims fleeing their countries for social or political reasons. Being an oppressed person and a victim of compelling social and political conditions does not give you the right to be a weak person in the West by following and practicing what is against your Islamic religion or creating a personality that is far from your true identity and religion.

Due to the fact that estrangement is an unhealthy social practice among male and female victimized Muslims in the West, this paper, however, moves the lens to the scope of estrangement through a victimized female escaping from tribal and conservative Bedouin societies such as Jordan in which Faqir's novel is set. In the following section, two noticeable standpoints of estrangement, namely: physical estrangement and cultural estrangement, along with Islamic standpoints are highlighted and analyzed within the scope of the aforesaid novel respectively.

4. Textual Analysis:

5.1 Physical Estrangement

Estrangement as a social and personal problem experienced by several Arab Muslims living in the west is evident in various Arab writers' literary works in general and Jordanian writers in particular. In Faqir's literary adopted work, Salma's journey from Jordan to England is a precise representation of the physical and cultural dimensions of the act of estrangement among these Arab Muslim migrants. The physical estrangement or dislocation is primarily evident in Salma's decision to move from an Arab Muslim country to a western country crossing Lebanon, Cyprus, and France. In Lebanon, upon seeing the new strange surroundings for the first time in her life, Salma asks "Where was I? How far was I from my mother? How far was I from her? Where are we?"

How far are we from my country?" (p. 82-83). Having sunk in deep thinking, she answers "We are north of Beirut, on the coast of the Mediterranean. Your country is further south, almost south-east with several hours' drive" (p. 84). Once she learns that she is no longer in her home country, this evokes nostalgia for her home in Hima, saying "I shall go back one day" (p. 84).

Going through new surroundings away from the homeland's familiarity leads Salma to experience the physical estrangement exemplified by the feeling of losing home and homeland immediately after her gloomy departure. The lights shining from the Lebanese kerosene lamps remind Salma with all her much-loved parts; her mother, her teacher, and her Hima until she finally settles in Exeter, England. Though Salma has spent more than a decade in England, her mother still lives in her mind, her past, and her memories, saying "I miss her horribly" (p. 289). Precisely, Salma's movement from the East to the West in general and from Jordan to England in particular is a physical dislocation for her. The feelings of estrangement have swept her through her new surroundings which make her long for home. Salma's journey from Jordan, one of the four countries of the area of Levant, to England affects the construction of her identity as an Arab Muslim due to the new cultural and personal experiences she goes through and the new people she comes across. With her final decision to position herself in England as her permanent new home, Salma has no choice but to fine-tune her identity along the lines of her new environment. Accurately, she has committed several misdeeds contrary to the teachings of Islam such as removing her veil to secure work, replacing loose clothes with skimpy clothing to work at a bar, and starting to drink alcohol. Another act contrary to the teachings required by a Muslim is evident in Salma's decision to pray in churches in England though she is a Muslim. "A modern society like postcolonial Britain where Salma moves to live is constantly changing thereby impacting the identities of its inhabitants. "This implies that identity's formation process of any person is impacted by the society, as one's identity cannot be fixed but undergoes transformations according to the new environment one inhabits" (Onyango, 2016 p. 45).

The feelings and aspects of estrangement are gleaned from her failure to adhere to the teachings of Islam in England and lack of strength to be a pious Muslim who affects and is affected by the people positively. With all her attempts to attain the adaptability of the new home in England, Salma is always viewed as an unwanted stranger who does not belong to England. Back in her early days of youth in Hima, Salma does not realize that being a Muslim in the remote village of Hima requires her to completely cover herself in her clothes to cover her body from male villagers. Since Salma has failed to completely cover her body, her father used to alert her "Your breasts are like melons, cover them up!" (p. 13).

This incident elucidates that Salma has been unable to understand the prevailing conservative and Islamic values of the society that impels women to completely cover her body so that males in the village are not attracted to her. To avoid suffering from the bad consequences of the wrath of her bad-tempered brother, Salma must hunch her back to conceal her breasts. Like other women living in a tribal community, Salma is powerless, marginalized, and helpless against the patriarchal society. Mahmoud, tribal and conservative beliefs, and the teachings of Islam do not deter Salma from getting involved in a forbidden sexual relationship with her lover out of marriage. Although Salma views Hima home, she has been unable to integrate into her society because of its rigid tribal and conservative nature and restrictions. In light of the above explanation, it is apparent that Salma experiences physical estrangement in Hima and the bad memories of Hima while living in England. Salma's miserable life and the ongoing cycle of feelings of estrangement in Hima transform her staying in England into a nightmare, fear, and isolation from her Arab Muslim identity.

5.2 Cultural Estrangement

The cultural estrangement in Salma's life begins when she arrives at the religious foundation in Lebanon. At first, she dresses up in clothes in a new style different from the loose clothing she is used to wearing while living in Hima. In her new clothes, she feels and looks different, saying "I put on pants and a bra, which I had never worn before. I put on the pair of blue jeans and the T-shirt Françoise had given me, tied my hair into a ponytail, tied my white veil around my head and walked out of the bathroom: a new, clean, awkward woman, conscious of the tight elastic around her hips and breasts (p. 87).

Being used to the conservative dressing style of loose pantaloons and long dresses, Salma as a Muslim completely feels out of the cast in clothing featured with tight elastic around her breasts and hips. Also, being a Muslim woman orders her to completely cover her hair whenever she is out of the house, but she defies the teachings of Islam by wearing her hair in a ponytail style though she, like other female Muslims, is required to conceal her hair. Her new experience with a new secular culture in England estranges her from the eastern conservative culture that she only knows. In her mind, a new identity is acquired in light of her new style of dressing leading to describe herself as a "new figure" because she never dresses in this dressing style before and as an awkward figure because she feels strange in her new style of clothes. In the friends and dining gatherings, the Nuns used to laugh at her because she quickly eats with her hands as Françoise, who is one of the nuns, says "Nobody is chasing you with a stick in his hand, eat slowly" (p. 92). The eastern habits of eating still live in Salma who eats with her bare hands unlike other Arab nuns living in England eating with cutlery pieces because they have previously embraced the western culture. As a result of these embarrassing personal situations

between Salma and other Arab nuns, Salma with her naïve character turns into a subject of laughter due to her strange practices resultant from the Arab culture.

Being an alien in England complicates Salma's life and makes it difficult in all real-life situations, saying "No, it was not easy living here in England as an alien, which was how the immigration officer had described me" (p. 37). Since her arrival in England escaping from the scandal, Hima, and its people, Salma faces several problems to adapt to the new life study and food in England, saying "I had tasted my first fish and chips, but my mountainous Arab stomach could not digest the fat, which floated in my tummy for days. Salma resisted, but Sally must adapt" (p.9). Lastly, Salma recognizes the significance of adapting to the new English cuisine to have a successful job and life in her new country.

Once upon a day at the backpacker's motel, the doorkeeper enters Salma's room in the company of Miss Parvin who asks about the homeland of Salma, where the porter responds "Somewhere in the Middle East. Fucking Arabic! She rode a camel from Arabia to this dump in Exeter" (15). This incident, which is full of racist scent, is a simple reminder to Salma that you belong to the Arab land and will experience situations and attitudes based on racism, discrimination, and stereotyping in your new land of England. In one of the wintry nights, Salma had to pretend to be asleep when Parvin, who will be her roommate, says "I am not going to share a room with an Arab" (15). These behaviors of racism are an immoral and disgusting way of jogging Salma's memory that she does not belong to and is not rooted in the English society and that she is only the so-called "Other".

An additional estrangement confronting Salma is when she does not understand some English words while looking for a job in English newspapers as the opening reads "*A sales girl required presentable with good command of English*". In this situation, Salma looks up the new words to her such as presentable and command in the dictionary, saying "I was neither presentable nor able to speak English well. Nothing that would suit a woman like me with no looks, no education, no experience, and no letters of recommendation" (17). Since her arrival in England, Salma is still unable to acquire the English language, which has always been the language of imperialism which is an essential evil to successfully manage her life in England. Importantly, what adds to her estrangement is having the appearance of an Arab girl, who is seen unattractive in a society full of signs of the Western attractive beauty. Also, Salma's conscious journey with estrangement is an endless sad story because wherever she goes in England, people find difficulties to recognize her identity as when she first meets Jim who begins guessing her homeland country, saying "Where do you come from?" "Guess?"

The list, as usual, included every country on earth except my own. "Nicaragua? France? Portugal? Greece? Surely Russia?" (68). Though several countries have been mentioned by Jim, he is still incapable of correctly recognizing the country Salma belongs to.

It is gleaned from the aforesaid excerpts of Faqir's novel that Salma has experienced estrangement in Jordan and England as well. She has been a victim of the physical and cultural estrangement in the east and the west. Though estrangement causes several problems to her related to the ability of adaptability to habits of eating cuisine, dressing, learning English, and identity, Salma has always been required to preserve her Islamic identity by practicing the teachings of Islam in all her real-life situation. Salma is a Muslim who is required to show people the strength of the teachings of Islam in managing the life of a Muslim in every time and place. This is evident in the Holy Qur'an that elucidated the Islamic standpoint about accepting others when living in a non-Muslim country such as Salma in England. The Holy Qur'an says "And we have not sent you, [O Muhammad], except as a mercy to the worlds" (21:107). Also, the Holy Qur'an states "And if your Lord had willed, He could have made mankind one community; but they will not cease to differ" (11:118). The aforementioned Qur'anic verses assert that Prophet Muhammad has been sent by Allah to spread mercy, lenience, respect, and mentality of accepting others from different religions.

As seen in the novel, physical and cultural estrangement is a pervasive phenomenon among female Muslim migrants such as Jordanian women. The novel presents the troubling situation where female Muslim migrants' rights and needs are ignored in the west because they disregard their Islamic identity and unfollow the teachings of Islam which are the solution to their personal and social problems inside and outside their countries. Faqir sheds light on the fact that female Muslim migrants in general and Jordanian women in particular are victims of a patriarchal social context that exploits them in the east and estranges them in the west.

5. Conclusion:

By presenting Salma as a protagonist who was born and raised in an unfair familial condition and later estranged by her society, Fadia Faqir highlights to Muslim and non-Muslim readers the issue of estrangement currently

happening among Arab Muslim women in general and Jordanian women in particular including Jordan. The estrangement of Salma by her brother and other individuals representing patriarchal mentality in the society is a clear example of how Arab Muslim women are victimized once they no longer apply the teachings of Islam in their daily life situations inside and outside their native countries.

Our reading of the novel concentrates on how Faqir makes tremendous efforts to highpoint the crisis of estrangement which is one of the social and personal problems Arab Muslim women undergo due to the non-application of the teachings of Islam in their daily real-life situations inside and outside their homeland. Indubitably, Faqir's description of estrangement through the physical and cultural aspects of estrangement of Salma opens new venues for the current and future readers to identify other unhealthy social, personal, and identity phenomena evidently related to the lack of employment of the teachings of Islam in Muslims' life. Salma's estrangement and escape, along with her weak identity seen in Hima, Jordan and Exeter, England do not only show her victimization, marginalization, and disempowerment but also provides an insight into the uncountable negative consequences related to the weak application of teachings of Islam. Therefore, Muslims' social ills such as estrangement must be read from an Islamic standpoint together with social theories due to the fact that they stem from social complexities and ills.

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